

ISic2981

I.Sicily inscription 2981

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.10

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175489

1. [— — — —] Ν [— — —]

2. [— — —]υκος Ν [— — —]

3. [— — — —]ΝΑ Κ [— — —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645334

PHI 175489

Bibliography

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L.

(eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.56

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